

BRIGHT
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Funded by
the European Union
GA Nr. 101060075

Advancing Sustainability in EU Agriculture within a Safe and Just Operating Space

25 July 2025

Key messages

EU agriculture faces multiple complex challenges: climate change, environmental pressures, trade dynamics, and structural shifts in technology and demand. These challenges must be managed within ecological limits and social fairness — the "Safe and Just Operating Space" (SJOS).

Multi-level policy coherence is essential, spanning agricultural, climate, environmental, and trade policies, to effectively support sustainable agriculture without unintended negative effects.

Technological innovation and policy design are crucial tools to shape sustainable transitions. Early insights show how technology, structural changes, and demand-side shifts influence agricultural outcomes.

Advanced modelling and scenario analysis enable policymakers to explore future pathways and trade-offs, supporting evidence-based decisions.

A clear roadmap is needed to integrate research, innovation, and policy to navigate the complex challenges and keep EU agriculture within the SJOS, ensuring long-term food security, environmental health, and social equity.

BrightSpace develops operational concepts and indicators for SJOS to assess agricultural sustainability in policy futures comprehensively, integrating economic, social and environmental dimensions.

The Issue: Navigating the Challenges of EU Agriculture

European agriculture stands at a crossroads. It must provide enough healthy food, maintain rural livelihoods, and contribute to economic growth — all while reducing greenhouse gas emissions, protecting biodiversity, and adapting to climate change. Added to this are shifting global trade patterns and evolving consumer demands.

Current policies and strategies often address these challenges separately, leading to fragmented approaches and sometimes unintended trade-offs. Without a holistic framework, there is a risk of overshooting environmental limits or creating social inequities, threatening the resilience and sustainability of the EU food system.

The concept of a **Safe and Just Operating Space (SJOS)** frames these challenges by combining ecological boundaries with social foundations. This means EU agriculture should operate within planetary limits (safe) while guaranteeing fair access to resources and opportunities (just).

POLICY BRIEF #01

Why is this important?

The sustainability of EU agriculture directly affects Europe's economy, health, environment, and global leadership in climate action. Achieving this balance is urgent because: **Economic and environmental risks are escalating**: soil degradation, water scarcity, biodiversity loss, and climate change impacts put agriculture's future productivity at risk. **Social equity matters**: farmers, rural communities, and consumers need fair access to resources, markets, and innovation benefits. **Policy complexity requires better integration**: agriculture is linked to climate, environment, and trade policies. Effective strategies demand coordinated, multi-dimensional approaches. **Technology and innovation offer pathways** to reduce negative impacts and enhance productivity, but they must be carefully assessed for social and environmental consequences.

The **BrightSpace project**, through its research and modelling efforts, contributes essential tools and knowledge to inform this transition.

What can policy makers do?

Adopt an integrated Safe and Just Operating Space framework for EU agriculture that guides all related policies and strategies. Use operational indicators from BrightSpace to test future policy scenarios.

Promote multi-level policy coherence by aligning agricultural, climate, environmental, and trade policies to avoid conflicting incentives and support holistic sustainability.

Support innovation and responsible technology adoption, assessing not only productivity gains but also social and environmental impacts to ensure equitable benefits.

Invest in advanced modelling and scenario tools like those developed by BrightSpace to explore policy options, anticipate trade-offs, and design adaptive strategies.

Engage stakeholders across the food system, including farmers, researchers, industry, and consumers, to co-create and implement sustainable pathways.

Plan for structural change and demand shifts by supporting rural development, diversification, and consumer awareness aligned with sustainability goals.

Encourage transparency and knowledge sharing to build trust and ensure evidence-based policymaking.

A joint Position Paper by three Horizon Europe projects

This policy brief accompanies the publication of the position paper *"Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security - An economic modellers' perspective"* jointly written by the Horizon Europe projects **LAMASUS**, **BrightSpace** and **ACT4CAP27**. This joint paper synthesises the insights of leading agri-economic modelling teams to guide future CAP development. It identifies five *Priority Action Areas (PAAs)* — income & resilience, nutrient autonomy, trade, innovation in the bioeconomy, and digitalisation — and proposes future directions for modelling tools to better assess complex policy trade-offs. The paper also outlines a *forward-looking modelling agenda* including: greater integration of environmental and economic data, better representation of innovation and consumer shifts, and enhanced systems-level understanding of the agri-food bioeconomy. The paper serves as a contribution to current and upcoming discussions on the EU's Common Agricultural Policy post-2027, European food system transformation, and strategic autonomy to ensure that agriculture remains a foundational pillar of the EU economy and food system — while operating within ecological limits and supporting social fairness. The BrightSpace project's unique contribution to the position paper lies in its *operationalisation of the Safe and Just Operating Space (SIOS) concept for agriculture*, providing practical tools and modelling approaches that integrate economic, social and environmental dimensions.

Access the
perspective
paper

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413131>

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References and further reading

<https://act4cap27.eu>
<https://brightspace-project.eu/>
<https://www.lamasus.eu/>